

Developments in direct nanopatterning of graphene; Towards direct write.

Szymon Abrahamczyk* Ondřej Sakreida Alicja Bachmatiuk Grażyna Simha Martynková Mark H. Rümmeli*

Dr. Szymon Abrahamczyk

EBEAM Centre, CNT, CEET, VŠB TUO, Ostrava, 708 00, Czechia

Email Address: szymon.piotr.abrahamczyk@vsb.cz

Prof. Dr. Mark H. Rümmeli

EBEAM Centre, CNT, CEET, VŠB TUO, Ostrava, 708 00, Czechia

The Leibniz Institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden (IFW Dresden), Helmholtzstr. 20, Dresden, D-01069, Germany

Soochow Institute for Energy and Materials InnovationS (SIEMIS), Optoelectronics and Energy & Collaborative Innovation Center of Suzhou Nano Science and Technology, and Key Laboratory of Advanced Carbon Materials and Wearable Energy Technologies of Jiangsu Province, School of Energy, Soochow University, Suzhou, 215006, China. Email Address: mhr1@vsb.cz

Ing. Ondřej Sakreida

EBEAM Centre, CNT, CEET, VŠB TUO, Ostrava, 708 00, Czechia

Prof. Dr. Alicja Bachmatiuk

EBEAM Centre, CNT, CEET, VŠB TUO, Ostrava, 708 00, Czechia

Faculty of Chemistry, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Wybrzeże Wyspiarskiego 27, Wrocław 50-370, Poland

Prof. Grażyna Simha Martynková

Nanotechnology Centre, CEET, VŠB-TUO, 708 33, Czechia

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Abstract

Graphene, with its exceptional electronic, mechanical, and thermal properties, remains a cornerstone material for next-generation nanoelectronics. However, conventional lithographic approaches to graphene patterning are fraught with challenges, including contamination, alignment complexity, and scalability constraints. This review critically examines the evolving landscape of direct-write graphene technologies, focusing on forefront strategies such as focused electron beam-induced deposition (FEBID), polymer-to-graphene (P2G) conversion, focused ion beam (FIB) modification, and laser-assisted graphitisation. These techniques represent a departure from traditional top-down or transfer-based methods by enabling bottom-up, spatially resolved patterning without intermediary masking steps. Particular attention is devoted to the physicochemical mechanisms that underlie electron- and photon-mediated graphitisation, the role of precursor chemistry and substrate interactions, as well as the influence of beam parameters on sp²-carbon content and structural ordering. The review further delineates the limitations intrinsic to current methodologies, including partial graphitisation, resolution fidelity, and hardware constraints, and proposes a roadmap to achieve truly 'direct' graphene writing. This includes in situ processing under controlled environments, advanced beam control systems, and the adoption of catalytic and graphitisable precursors. Collectively, this work provides a comprehensive foundation for the rational design of next-generation nanofabrication protocols and underscores the transformative potential of direct-write techniques in enabling scalable, high-fidelity graphene-based devices.

1 Introduction

1.1 What is graphene?

Graphene was first confirmed and isolated as a stable free-standing structure by Novoselov et al. in 2004 using the famous Scotch tape method.[1–3] This marked the beginning of the 'gold rush' in graphene research has exploded in physics, materials science and engineering, leading to extensive studies on its applications in electronics, nanotechnology, and energy storage.[4, 5] The non-exhaustive list of notable developments would include advanced synthesis techniques such as chemical vapour deposition (CVD), epitaxial growth on SiC, pyrolysis, liquid phase exfoliation (LPE), polymer-to-graphene conversion (P2G), reduction of graphene oxide *etc.* [6], elucidation of the electronic and quantum properties of graphene (graphene transistors, quantum effects, high-frequency electronics)[7], introduction into materials science and engineering (composites, energy storage, thermal management)[8] and biomedical and environmental applications (biosensors, drug delivery, water filtration and desalination)[9].

Graphene's unique structure confers remarkable properties, including high electrical conductivity, mechanical strength, and thermal stability, making it ideal for nanotechnology applications.[2] A single pristine layer of graphene (SLG) is a zero-bandgap material allowing a conduction of massless Dirac fermions making it an excellent conductor with electrical conductivity of around 10^5 S m^{-1} , comparable to that of metallic silver in bulk approx. $6.2 \times 10^7 \text{ S m}^{-1}$. [2, 10] The deterioration of the conductivity of metals in nanoscale due to quantum size effects and surface scattering of the electrons (down to $< 10^4 \text{ S m}^{-1}$) provides single layer pristine graphene a significant benefit for application in nanometric-scale electronics as a conductor.[11, 12] However, this advantage is highly dependent on the quality and fabrication method of the graphene used.

The quality of graphene often refers to the number of layers, the presence of defects, the chemical uniformity, and the size of the graphene domain.[13, 14] For example, a double layer graphene has an order of magnitude lower electrical conductivity (10^4 S m^{-1}) than that of SLG.[15] While in SLG the conduction (CB) and valence bands (VB) are touching at a single Dirac point, the graphene bilayer exhibits interlayer interactions (van der Waals and $\pi - \pi$ spin-orbit coupling) in effect creating a finite bandgap ($< 0.2 \text{ eV}$), making the electrons behave much more as particles with an effective mass.[16] Further stacking and defects will also affect the conductivity of the synthesised graphene, making this material difficult to process.[17–19]

Graphene defects are typically classified into several types: point defects such as vacancies[21, 24], interstitial defects, substitutions[25–27], or adatoms[28]; line defects such as grain boundaries[29] and dislocations[22, 29]; plane defects such as multilayer regions, folds, and wrinkles[30]; structural distortions, including Stone-Wales defects[31], ripples, and corrugations; and chemical and functional defects such as oxidised and hydrogenated areas, as well as edge defects[20]. These dopants and defect states will significantly affect the electronic structure of graphene and introduce a band gap.[13, 32] Figure 1 illustrates how this doping might appear in a graphene sheet. These, depending on the situation, can be considered as unwanted defects that deteriorate the quality of graphene, or dopants that make graphene a material with a highly tuneable bandgap.[13, 33]

Chemical doping can be introduced into graphene by incorporating heteroatoms (B[34], N[34–36], P[37, 38], O[39], S[40], F[41], Cl[42, 43], Al[27], Co[44], H[45, 46], Si) into the graphene lattice that donate or accept electrons, functionalisation of graphene (oxidation to rGO) that disrupts the graphene's sp^2 hybridisation, or even adsorption of metal atoms, particles, or even molecules that would transfer their charge to the graphene surface. The chemical doping gives a lot of control over the type and degree of doping, allowing bandgap tuning from 0 - 2.9 eV.

However, structural changes such as single or multiple vacancies that allow for chemical homogeneity are not currently difficult to introduce with controlled processes. These can alter the electronic properties of graphene by the introduction of strains, rotations, and lattice mismatches. [47]

The last but not least type of graphene quality parameter is its graphene domain size. Small graphene domains have significantly orders of magnitude lower carrier mobilities as a result of phonons and impurity scattering contributing to resistivity, whereas in large graphene domains the transport is more

Figure 1: A) Simplified chemical structure of a graphene sheet, and examples of possible doping/defect states. All the image have a white scale bar representing 2 nm. The edge effect, point vacancy, and multiple vacancy TEM images are reproduced from Warner et al.[20], Robertson et al.[21], and Lehtinen et al.[22], respectively. B) Recognised processes used for graphene fabrication. Interpretation of similar figures from citations [23] and [17].

ballistic.[1] The small domains domains below 10 nm can even experience quantum confinement effects shifting the Dirac cone to opening a bandgap.[48] Furthermore, the alignment and orientation of graphene domains, especially in polycrystalline films, can lead to the formation of grain boundaries and twisting between domains, significantly impacting both charge mobility and structural strength. Depending on the twist angle, these twisted domains can display moiré superlattice patterns, giving rise to novel electronic effects, including flat bands and correlated insulating phases, as seen in twisted bilayer graphene. Consequently, producing large-area, single-crystal graphene is crucial for high-performance electronic and optoelectronic applications. These monocrystalline graphene sheets reduce grain boundary scattering and maintain graphene's inherent properties, such as its extremely high carrier mobility and linear band structure. Significant effort has been invested in refining CVD methods to manage nucleation density and growth kinetics, enabling centimetre-scale single-crystal domains.

The quality of graphene can be quantified using multitechnique approach combining structural characterisation (Raman spectroscopy, TEM and AFM), electrical properties (4-point probe, Kelvin probe and cAFM), chemical purity and dopant quantification (XPS, FTIR and TGA). Figure 2 shows the different stages of graphitisation of organic, carbon-rich materials. These changes can be monitored as a change in the line shape of a Raman spectrum, as can be seen further in Figure 3. In amorphous carbon, the bands are very broad, the 2D peak is usually not onset, and the positions of the peaks also differ. In graphitic material, the full width at half-maxima (FWHM) of the G and 2D bands becomes much sharper. For few-layer graphene, interpreting the deconvolution of the G, D, and 2D bands allows for quality assessment.

1.2 Timeline of graphene fabrication methods

Although the term 'graphene' gained prominence in the early 2000s, theoretical interest in its properties dates back to mid-20th century. For instance, Wallace predicted in 1947 its unique band structure, and Semenoff in 1984 described the massless Dirac fermion behaviour of electrons in graphene.[50, 51] Since its first isolation by Geim and Novoselov in 2004, graphene has driven advances in a wide range of fields,

Figure 2: A schematic representation of degree of graphitisation. Recreated from the graphic abstract by Schuepfer et al.[49]

from electronics to nanotechnology.[1, 3, 5]

The past two decades have allowed for the development of advanced synthesis techniques. Current graphene fabrication procedures can be divided into various groups, including exfoliation (physical, chemical, or mechanical *etc.*), decomposition of organic materials (catalytic or non-catalytic), chemical reduction of graphene oxide (GO) into reduced GO (rGO) or epitaxial growth (CVD).[17] Graphene fabrication methods are usually segregated into bottom-up and top-down approaches, as was done by Yan et al. and Wu et al.[17, 23] For the purpose of this review, the graphene fabrication techniques were segregated into bulk graphene fabrication (exfoliation), film growth (CVD, PVD) and direct graphene writing (with laser, electrons *etc.*) as lustrated in the Figure 1.

1.2.1 Graphene fabrication from bulk materials

Fabrication of graphene often entails the breakdown of bulk graphite into individual graphene layers or small stacks, which distinguishes it markedly from bottom-up approaches that synthesise graphene from molecular precursors or carbon-rich materials.

Among bulk graphene fabrication strategies, exfoliation is predominant and encompasses mechanical, chemical, and liquid-phase methods. Table 1 contains summary of the key exfoliation techniques used to fabricate bulk graphene. The most iconic example is mechanical exfoliation via the "Scotch tape method", first used by Novoselov et al. to isolate pristine monolayer graphene, an achievement that later earned the Nobel Prize in Physics (2010).[1, 2] Although this method remains the benchmark for producing defect-free monolayers, its lack of scalability limits its industrial applicability.[52]

In contrast, chemical exfoliation introduces intercalating agents, such as acids or alkali metals, to expand the interlayer spacing within graphite, followed by sonication to yield graphene sheets.[53–55] This approach, often used in the reduction of graphene oxide (GO), is scalable but typically introduces a high density of structural defects, necessitating further post-treatment.

Liquid phase exfoliation (LPE), another scalable route, disperses graphite in solvents under sonication to overcome van der Waals interactions.[56–58] The surface energy of the solvent must be carefully matched with that of graphene to maintain stable dispersions and prevent reaggregation.[59, 60]

While these exfoliation techniques have facilitated the integration of graphene into commercial products, they still suffer from critical limitations, including poor control over domain size, number of layers, and defect density. Moreover, patterning of graphene fabricated using these methods is nearly exclusively possible by lithography, lift-off or precise transfer.

Table 1: Summary of exfoliation techniques used to fabricate bulk graphene.

Exfoliation	Quality	Applications	Pros	Cons	References
<i>Scotch tape method</i>	Pristine monolayers, large domains, minimal defects	Fundamental research, transistors, quantum devices	Highest quality graphene, ideal for research	Low yield, not scalable, manual process	[1, 2]
<i>LPE</i>	Small flakes, variable defects, few-layer graphene	Coatings, composites, inks, energy storage	Scalable, cost-effective, solution-processable	High defect density, solvent contamination	[56–60]
<i>Chemical graphene oxide reduction</i>	High defect density, oxidized, reduced conductivity	Bulk graphene oxide, energy applications, membranes	Large-scale production, inexpensive	Reduces electrical properties, requires post-treatment	[61–63]
<i>Electrochemical</i>	Moderate defect density, few-layer graphene	Flexible electronics, supercapacitors	Environmentally friendly, scalable	Difficult thickness control, lower quality than mechanical	[64–66]
<i>Intercalation-assisted</i>	Layer-by-layer exfoliation, lower defects	Battery electrodes, printed electronics	Selective exfoliation, controlled quality	Requires specialized chemicals, limited scalability	[67, 68]

1.2.2 Film growth

Graphene may also be synthesised directly on a substrate, a process commonly known as bottom-up growth. Graphene synthesis via bottom-up methodologies primarily involves the incorporation of carbon atoms into the graphene lattice through surface-catalysed chemical processes.

A widely adopted method is chemical vapour deposition (CVD), in which gaseous carbon sources like methane or acetylene disintegrate on catalytic metallic surfaces such as copper or nickel, facilitating the production of high-quality monolayer graphene. This technique offers substantial control over the layer count, crystallinity, and domain size of the graphene films produced.[17]

Some new approaches in CVD also implement polymer-to-graphene conversion, in which a thin film of a polymer (most often PMMA) is deposited onto a substrate from solution.[69, 70] The film is then converted into graphene with the help of elevated temperature (> 800 °C), application of reducing agent (H_2 and Ar gas mix) and catalysts (Cu, Ni, Cr[71]).

Factors such as the temperature of the substrate, the deposition rate, and the type of metal catalyst employed play roles in determining the quality and number of graphene layers formed. For example, Wu et al. indicate that Cu substrates are conducive to the growth of single-layer graphene due to their low carbon solubility, while nickel tends to produce multiple layers through carbon dissolution and precipitation upon cooling.

Epitaxial growth on SiC substrates yields high-quality, wafer-scale graphene with excellent crystallinity and minimal defects, but it is hindered by its high cost and limited scalability due to substrate constraints and the need for ultra-high temperatures (>1200 °C).[72] Pyrolysis of carbon-rich materials, particularly polymer precursors, provides a facile, transfer-free route towards direct graphene formation on various substrates, and it can be spatially confined for patterning, but it suffers from limited structural control and a higher degree of disorder, making it less suitable for electronic-grade applications. [73, 74] Collectively, while epitaxy ensures quality, CVD balances quality and scalability, and pyrolysis offers simplicity and integration versatility at the expense of structural precision.

1.3 Graphene processing and patterning limitations

The commercialisation of graphene-based electronic devices has been hindered by a series of fabrication and scalability challenges. Chief among these is the reliance on conventional lithographic processes, which often involve multiple steps, such as masking, etching, and transfer, which introduce defects, contamination, or alignment issues, particularly when aiming for nanoscale precision or heterogeneous integration[77]. Moreover, high-performance device fabrication commonly requires the synthesis of uniform large-area monolayer graphene via CVD, a process constrained by high temperatures, specific substrate compatibility, and limited patterning capabilities[69, 78]. These limitations collectively reduce throughput and increase production costs.

Figure 3: A) SEM image and a Raman spectrum of graphene grown using epitaxial growth on SiC.[75] B) HRTEM image and Raman spectrum of a graphene obtained as a result of pyrolysis of green tea extract at 1100 °C.[74] C) SEM image and a Raman spectrum of a monolayer graphene sheet grown using CVD and transferred onto Si.[76] All Raman spectra were reproduced and digitised from plots in the citations [74–76]

Numerous attempts have been made to improve the processability of graphene, one of which involves poly(acrylonitrile) (PAN) as a transfer medium.[79] The study investigates the use of PAN as a transfer medium for wafer-scale graphene. The authors found that PAN can effectively serve as a transfer medium, simultaneously facilitating the encapsulation and transfer of large-area graphene films. This approach addresses common issues in graphene transfer processes, such as contamination and mechanical damage, thereby improving the quality and scalability of graphene-based applications.[79] Transferred graphene would still need to be patterned in conventional ways.

An innovative technique called Thermal, Electrical, and Water Assisted Reaction (TEAWAR) facilitates the transformation of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) and similar organic residues into graphene.[80] The TEAWAR process leverages the synergistic effects of thermal energy, electrical stimulation, and water mediation to achieve this conversion. This approach offers a novel pathway for graphene synthesis, potentially enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of graphene production from polymeric materials.

Attempts to create graphene-rich inks for 3D printing were reviewed by Jiang et al. The review outlines recent developments in 3D printing of graphene-based materials and their applications in energy storage and conversion devices and discusses the extrusion-based direct ink writing technique, emphasising the rheological behaviour of graphene oxide (GO) dispersions and strategies for preparing printable GO inks. The review highlights how 3D printing enables the design of advanced electrode architectures, potentially improving the performance of energy storage devices.[8] This methodology, however does not align with the scope of this review and graphene-ink based additive manufacturing methods will not be considered further.

Figure 4: Venn diagram showing various advantages shared between EBL, CVD, Additive manufacturing (AM) with electron beam induced deposition sharing all these. The processes are also summarised as diagrams where CVD was recreated from Esmaeilpour et al.[81] and AM from Manokruang[82].

2 Focused electron beam induced deposition (FEBID)

2.1 Fundamentals of electron-material interactions

Focused electron beam-induced deposition (FEBID) relies on intricate interactions between the electron beam and, for example, reactive gas, thin films, and even substrates, to transform materials and deposit it directly and in a controlled manner on a nanoscale. These processes resemble the ones occurring during electron beam lithography (EBL) which has similar *modus operandi*, thus both of these research areas use similar approaches and terminology. Both primary electrons (PE) and secondary electrons (SE), as well as substrate-mediated effects, play critical roles in these material transformations. PEs, typically generated at voltages between 0.1–30 kV, penetrate the substrate and lose energy via inelastic collisions, generating cascades of secondary electrons (SEs) with energies usually below 50 eV. These SEs are largely responsible for the surface-localised dissociation of precursor molecules in FEBID due to their highly localised energy deposition. Higher energy PEs result in broader interaction volumes, whereas lower acceleration voltages confine the effect near the surface. Backscattered electrons (BSEs), more prominent on high-atomic-number substrates such as Cu or Ni, contribute to a lateral broadening of the deposition area.[83] In parallel, electron-induced ionisation leads to radiolysis, where precursor bonds can be cleaved to form radicals and volatile species such as CO, CO₂, and H₂O. The amount of electron radiation required to achieve the material transformation, called dose (D) is defined as:

$$D = \frac{1}{A} \int_0^t i(t) dt$$

where A is area, t is time, and i is current. Typically in EBL, this dose is a representation of the minimal value at which the resist (usually polymer) transforms by bond cleavage, or cross-linking. At high

doses, this residual carbon can transition into amorphous or sp^2 -rich carbon domains, setting the stage for graphene-like structures. For conversion of polymer to graphene (P2G) these values are expected to be much higher than for EBL as the reaction end is expected not as initial transformation but rather as complete graphitisation. In FEBID, this value indicates the amount of radiation needed to convert the gaseous precursor and deposit the solid onto a substrate *e.g.* by the removal of ligands from the precursor which makes it volatile or bond cleavage and formation of radicals that reassemble and deposit as solid.[84, 85] Although knock-on displacement typically requires electron energies above 80–100 keV—beyond the range of standard SEM-based EBID—lighter atoms like hydrogen and oxygen may still be displaced, contributing to the purification of the deposit. Substrate properties also significantly influence the process: conductive substrates (*e.g.*, Cu, Ni, doped Si) dissipate charge and often catalyse graphitisation, whereas insulating substrates (*e.g.*, SiO_2 , glass) can accumulate charge, leading to beam distortion. Variable pressure conditions with inert gases may help mitigate charging without interfering chemically. Substrate atomic number affects BSE yield and, consequently, the spatial extent of deposition. Importantly, catalytic substrates such as Cu can aid carbon atom diffusion and reorganisation, facilitating higher-quality graphene growth. Collectively, the combination of SE-driven dissociation, radiolytic decomposition, selective knock-on displacement, and catalytic substrate interaction would drive the success of EBID in forming graphene nanostructures.

2.2 Separation into graphitisable and non-graphitisable materials

The separation of graphitisable and non-graphitisable materials is a fundamental concept in carbon material science, particularly relevant to the fabrication of graphene and other graphitic structures.[86] Upon thermal treatment, carbon-rich precursors exhibit divergent structural transformations depending on their molecular structure and bonding characteristics.

Graphitisable materials, such as certain pitches and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and certain polymers, undergo structural reordering upon heating, eventually forming crystalline graphene layers with high stacking order and extended lateral dimensions. This transition is facilitated by the absence of cross-linking side groups and a high degree of aromaticity, allowing carbon atoms to rearrange into the thermodynamically favourable graphitic lattice. In contrast, non-graphitisable materials, PMMA, possess a cross-linked, amorphous structure due to the presence of heteroatoms and functional groups such as hydroxyls. These groups hinder the alignment and growth of ordered graphene layers, resulting in materials that remain largely disordered even at elevated temperatures. The distinction between these two classes of materials could be particularly significant in the context of electron beam processing, where the structural predisposition of the precursor determines the feasibility and quality of graphitisation, with direct implications for the electronic, optical and mechanical properties of the resulting carbon films.[86, 87]

It seems that the vast majority of research on polymer-to-graphene conversion is influenced by the research on electron beam lithography on PMMA as a resist material.[88]

2.3 Polymer-to-graphene (P2G) conversion using electron beam

EBID enables the direct transformation of polymeric precursors into graphenic materials through a combination of radiolytic and thermal effects.[89] Upon e-beam irradiation, the polymer matrix undergoes ionization and bond scission, producing free radicals that recombine to form a cross-linked, carbon-rich network. Simultaneously, dehydrogenation and deoxygenation expel heteroatoms such as hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen, enriching the sp^2 -carbon content. Polymers like PMMA, polystyrene, PAN, polyimides, and phenolic resists (*e.g.*, SU-8 or AZ5214) display distinct responses under EBID, influenced by their molecular structure. For instance, PMMA carbonizes into amorphous features, while PAN undergoes electron-induced cyclization, mimicking thermal stabilisation and yielding nitrogen-doped graphenic carbon.[88, 90, 91] Polyimides, rich in heteroatoms, can form porous, conductive graphite foams under high-dose irradiation.[92] Beyond chemical changes, the e-beam also induces localised heating via inelastic scattering, facilitating pyrolysis and bond reconfiguration. Substrate effects further influence this process; conductive metals like Cu or Ni not only dissipate heat but also catalyse dehydrogenation and induce planarisation.

Figure 5: A) The process flow diagram of the e-beam lithographic process for the fabrication of graphene nanostructures on copper substrate. Low-quality graphene was formed at step 3, and the high-quality graphene at step 6. B) Raman spectra of the sample at the different preparation stages Recreated from Bi et al.[88]

Post-irradiation annealing—typically at 300–800 °C in inert or reducing atmospheres—significantly enhances structural ordering and conductivity, driving the reorganisation of disordered carbon into graphitic domains. While EBID alone often yields amorphous or turbostratic carbon, sustained irradiation or thermal treatment promotes graphitisation, especially in the presence of catalytic substrates. The final material typically comprises nanocrystalline graphite or a mosaic of small graphene domains, with resistivities ranging from 10^{-4} to 10^{-3} Ω cm, which are sufficient for use in microelectrodes, sensors, and other functional carbon nanostructures. Thus, EBID offers a controllable, lithography-compatible method for bottom-up fabrication of graphenic nanomaterials, with tunable properties governed by precursor chemistry, electron dose, and thermal conditions.

2.4 Electron beam induced modifications in SAMs

Electron beam-induced modifications in self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) offer a powerful and versatile approach for tailoring surface chemistry and nanoscale patterning with high spatial resolution. Upon exposure to low-energy electron irradiation, typically below 100 eV, SAMs undergo a variety of physico-chemical transformations, including bond cleavage, desorption, cross-linking, and reorientation of molecular backbones. In particular, SAMs featuring carboxylic acid (CA) anchoring groups on coinage metal substrates such as silver have demonstrated pronounced susceptibility to electron-induced reactions. These modifications are driven by electron-stimulated cleavage of the carboxylate–metal bond, leading to partial or complete desorption of molecules, followed by the formation of a carbonaceous residue via cross-linking of the remaining organic fragments. The presence of aromatic backbones in CA-based SAMs enhances the propensity for cross-linking due to delocalised π -electrons, enabling the conversion of the monolayer into a robust, insoluble carbon nanomembrane. Furthermore, electron irradiation can induce significant conformational and orientational changes in the SAMs, such as reorientation or disordering of the molecular packing. These effects are highly dependent on the molecular structure, packing density, and energy and dose of the electron beam. Such controlled modifications are increasingly exploited in applications ranging from lithography and surface patterning to the fabrication of chemically and mechanically stable nanostructures[94–96]

Figure 6: (A) Scheme of the electron irradiation of oxo-G flakes on a SiO₂ (300 nm)|Si wafer. The colour code indicates the dose ranging from 50 to 800 mC cm⁻² for the beam energies between 2 and 30 keV. (B) Raman map of a film of oxo-G flakes mapping the full-width at half-maximum (Γ_D) of the Raman D peak after e-beam irradiation of different energy and doses. Red: broad D peaks (low quality, amorphous), blue narrow D peaks (better quality). (C) Raman map of the same area as in (B) of reduced oxo-G after FEBIP. Introduced areas of increased defect densities (red area) are permanent. Recreated from Schindler et al.[93]. (D) Schematic representation of the constituents and their functions in a self-assembled monolayer (SAM). (E) Electron beam induced modification of SAMs: (E) aliphatic SAMs; (F) aromatic SAMs; (G) aromatic SAMs with nitro termination. Figures from citation [94]

2.5 Gaseous precursors

Electron beam-induced graphene growth can also be performed using carbonaceous gases such as ethylene, acetylene, or phenanthrene being introduced into the electron microscope chamber. The focused electron beam dissociates these molecules, depositing carbon-rich material, eventually graphene. Graphene growth using TEM from VOC contamination has also been previously reported.[99] To our knowledge, this has not yet been achieved in a SEM setting.

In 2002, Kiyohara et al. used a mix gas of H₂ and CH₄ to directly write diamond onto a Si(100) wafer.[100] They used a in-house modified TOPCON DS-130S equipped with a sub-chamber where all gases were injected as shown in Figure 10. They found that the optimal concentration of CH₄ in the chamber was *ca.* 1 % for formation of sp³ carbon structures. Above that regime, the formation of more sp² carbon structures took place. This knowledge suggests potential direction of direct-write graphene from H₂ and CH₄ mix gas. The paper also showcases the use of Tempilstick as a method of determining local temperature changes.[100]

Other gaseous precursors can also be used to nucleate[97] or directly write[101] carbon-rich metal-based films and nanostructures. The carbon content depends on multiple variables including the precursor used (*e.g.* incomplete ligand stripping, CO cleavage), residual hydrocarbons in the chamber atmosphere, sample preparation methods, beam settings *etc.*, and most of them are in a porous state.[98, 101, 102] Although most of the carbon content in these structures is amorphous there is a potential for further conversion to graphene and creation of attractive composite materials, for example, for sensing applications.[102–105]

Figure 7: A) Schematic representation of the area-selective autocatalytic film growth. A seed layer is deposited using a focused electron beam to locally decompose the precursor on a substrate (top) at room temperature (30 °C) or (bottom) at elevated substrate temperatures.[97] B) Schematic illustrating different stages of ligand cleavage in the fragmentation of HFeCo₃(CO)₁₂ and two subsequent effects leading to (i) a composite formation by further electron bombardment or (ii) complete ligand stripping by a thermally activated process step resulting in a pure FeCo₃ alloy.[98]

3 Focused ion beam (FIB)

3.1 Fundamentals

Irradiation with focused ion beam (FIB) induces a range of modifications in graphene, depending on the ion species, energy, dose, and ambient environment.[106] At low ion doses, collisions between ions and carbon atoms primarily generate isolated point defects, such as vacancies or bond distortions, without significantly altering the overall morphology.[107] As the dose increases, these defects agglomerate into nanopores, and at sufficiently high doses, heavy-ion bombardment amorphises the carbon lattice and can eventually perforate or fully sputter the graphene sheet.[108] In addition to structural damage, certain ion species, such as gallium (Ga⁺) commonly used in FIB, can be implanted into graphene, causing strain, increasing defect density, and altering electronic properties such as the work function.[106] Lighter ions such as helium (He⁺) or neon (Ne⁺), while less likely to dope the lattice due to their chemical inertness, create finely controlled physical defects and allow for high-resolution patterning.[109] Reactive ions such as nitrogen (N⁺), boron (B⁺), or fluorine (F⁺) can covalently dope the lattice; for instance, low-energy N⁺ irradiation introduces pyridinic and graphitic nitrogen sites before vacancy formation dominates at higher fluences.[110] Ion irradiation can also induce localised stress and lattice distortions, with heavier ions causing bond rehybridization (from sp² to sp³) and occasionally forming adatoms or clusters (e.g., Ga or Cu) that further modify electrical and chemical behaviour.[111] Comparatively, Ga⁺ ions are highly efficient at sputtering (50 % sputtering yield) but simultaneously implants the Ga into graphene lattice doping the material, while He⁺ and Ne⁺ offer superior resolution and minimal chemical alteration (97 % of He⁺ ions are transmitted at high energies with no destructive effects), making them more suitable for precision nanopatterning.[112] Overall, the interplay between physical displacement and chemical interaction defines the structural and electronic transformations of graphene under FIB.[110–112]

Figure 8: **A**) Two edge dislocations are created via sputtering of carbon atoms and reorganization of the multi-vacancy structure. The upper panels show the original AC-HRTEM images with low-pass Fourier filtering applied and the lower panels show the same frames with maximum filtering applied for better visibility. In panel a, two atoms have been removed, forming a divacancy. In each subsequent panel b-e two more atoms have been removed and the defect has undergone considerable reorganization. In panel e, with ten missing atoms, the defect structure has reorganized into a dislocation dipole with two edge dislocations at its ends pointing away from each other. The scale bar is 1 nm. From Lehtinen et al.[22] **B**) (a) Smoothed AC-TEM image of the symmetric monovacancy, s-MV, with three edge C atoms. (b) DFT-calculated atomistic model and (c) multislice TEM image simulation corresponding to the structure in (a). (d) Smoothed AC-TEM image of the reconstructed monovacancy, r-MV, with one edge C atom. Yellow arrows indicate the zigzag axis containing the reconstruction. (e) DFT-calculated atomistic model and (f) multislice TEM image simulation corresponding to the structure in (e). Scale bar corresponds to 1 nm in all panels. From Robertson et al.[21] **C**) Schematic illustration of the steps involved in the fabrication of GDQD by HIM milling.(a) HIM SE image of a monolayer graphene flake with metal contacts and RIE-formed isolation lines. (b) HIM SE image of the etched isolation lines (dark lines in the figure) which are forming an area of $\sim 500 \text{ nm} \times 420 \text{ nm}$ on the flake that was left intact for the final HIM patterning step. From Kalhor et al.[113]

3.2 Graphene milling

Numerous studies have been conducted on the application of FIB for the milling of graphene and localised doping. Kalhor et al. used a helium ion microscope (HIM) to fabricate double quantum dots of graphene from mechanically exfoliated graphene supported on Si wafer patterned with a combined study of EBL and reactive ion etching (RIE) for CMOS applications.[113] HIM not only allowed for superior imaging resolution, but also allowed for graphene milling at the nanometre scale in scanning mode, which is often called helium ion beam milling (HIBM).[114] Schmidt et al. used a similar approach of HIBM to fabricate graphene nanoribbons with the first report of a functional device with characterisation of electrical properties[115] The research group was also able to achieve a graphene nanomesh with tuneable conductance using HIBM.[116] HIBM was also previously reported as fabrication method for nanoporous graphene for biosensing, in this case DNA.[117]

4 Laser-assisted patterning

4.1 Fundamentals

Figure 9: Mechanism of laser induced deposition. A schematic diagram showing that photochemical processes occur only at higher energy radiation (>390 nm) while photothermal processes happen in the regimes from IR to UV.[118, 119]

Laser-assisted graphene deposition fundamentally relies on two distinct physical mechanisms: photothermal and photochemical effects; whose dominance is determined by the photon energy of the laser source. These two regimes play a crucial role in determining the quality, morphology, and degree of graphitisation of the resulting material.[17, 118, 119]

In the photothermal regime, where the photon energy is below approximately 3.2 eV (wavelengths longer than 390 nm, *i.e.* visible and infrared lasers), the formation of graphene is driven primarily by localised heating. The carbon-rich precursor (often polymers such as polyimide) absorbs the laser energy, which is then converted to heat. This thermal energy initiates pyrolysis, fragmenting the polymer and leading to carbonisation once the temperature exceeds a critical threshold (approx. 2700 K). At this point, molecular fragments reorganise into sp^2 -bonded carbon networks characteristic of graphene. This regime follows Arrhenius-type behaviour: Higher laser power or slower scanning speeds enhance local temperature and graphitisation.[69, 70]

In contrast, the photochemical regime becomes relevant with ultraviolet (UV) lasers possessing photon energies above approx. 3.2 eV (wavelengths < 390 nm). In this regime, bond dissociation (*e.g.* of C–O, C=O, or C–N) can occur via direct photoexcitation, independent of thermal effects. UV photons can break chemical bonds directly at lower fluences, thereby reducing the temperature required for carbonisation. However, as laser fluence increases, photothermal effects again become significant, resulting in a

mixed photochemical–photothermal mechanism. This hybrid mechanism enables more efficient and precise graphene formation, as observed in excimer laser ablation studies.

At sufficient laser fluence and energy density, the irradiated precursor not only carbonises but evolves into a porous graphene foam due to rapid gas evolution (CO, CO₂, H₂O, etc.). This outgassing results in microporosity and a foam-like structure with vertically orientated, few-layer graphene sheets, known as laser-induced graphene (LIG). Although this structure is typically not atomically flat, its large surface area and exposed edges offer distinct advantages for sensing and energy applications.

The ultrafast, non-equilibrium nature of laser-induced graphene formation can trap structural defects. These are commonly observed as strong D-bands in Raman spectra. Nonetheless, post-treatment methods, such as rapid Joule flash heating, have demonstrated effectiveness in healing these defects, improving crystalline order, and enhancing electrical conductivity.

4.2 Laser type influence

Laser-assisted graphene synthesis can be achieved using various types of lasers, offering distinct processing advantages based on their wavelength, pulse duration, and interaction with carbon-rich precursors. Infrared CO₂ lasers (10.6 μm), with photon energies (~0.117 eV) far below typical bond dissociation energies, operate via a strongly photothermal mechanism. These deliver deep substrate heating, generating thick, porous few-layer graphene with a relatively low defect density, especially on polymers such as polyimide. Due to their long wavelength and thermal diffusion, CO₂ lasers are limited in spatial resolution (~100–200 μm), but are ideal for rapid, large-area graphene writing in ambient conditions, as demonstrated by Lin et al. and Ye et al.[120–122]. Visible lasers like 532 nm (green) are also predominantly photothermal, with moderate polymer absorption and intermediate feature resolution (~50 μm). These have been employed in laser chemical vapour deposition (LCVD) using metal substrates, such as Ni, to catalyse graphene growth, as shown by Chen et al., and in direct laser writing on PI films by Huang et al.

The near-UV regime (e.g. 355 nm), laser energy (~3.5 eV) begins to approach carbon bond dissociation energies, enabling partial photochemical interactions. This results in enhanced absorption in polymers and finer spatial resolution (~30–50 μm), although care must be taken to avoid substrate ablation. These lasers can produce more defective graphene, often with weaker 2D Raman bands, as reported by Wang et al. and Liu and Chen.[122, 125] Deep UV excimer lasers (e.g. 248 nm) extend this trend, offering strong photochemical activation (~5 eV per photon) and allowing bond scission without substantial heating. Used in inert atmospheres to prevent oxidation, deep UV lasers can write graphene with high spatial precision (<20 μm), especially useful in microelectronic applications, as demonstrated by Singleton et al., Yu et al. (2020).[126]

Femtosecond (fs) lasers, operating in the visible or near-IR/UV range, exploit ultrashort pulses (on the order of 10⁻¹⁵ s) to induce non-linear effects like multiphoton ionisation and microplasma formation. This confines energy deposition spatially and temporally, minimising thermal diffusion and allowing extremely fine feature writing (~10 μm or less). Femtosecond lasers have been used to produce hierarchically porous graphene with high surface area with degree of doping, as reported by Liu and Chen, although the resulting material often contains more edge defects (high D-band intensity) unless it is post-annealed.[125] Lastly, blue diode lasers (405–450 nm), commonly found in low-cost engravers, provide an accessible photothermal tool for LIG on absorptive substrates, although their lower power and weaker absorption often yield lower graphene quality. These are more prevalent in hobbyist or educational settings, with few high-quality scientific reports to date.

5 Conclusions and future work

FIBM, in particular HIBM, while demonstrating considerable potential for the direct writing of various materials, is better suited for milling and doping applications in the context of graphene, particularly through the use of reactive ions such as Ga⁺. However, its utility in direct graphene writing remains limited due to structural damage and ion contamination, which compromise the integrity of the sp² network.

Figure 10: A) shows a schematic diagram of the localized EB CVD system, which was manufactured in-house by modifying a conventional scanning electron microscope (TOPCON DS-130S). A sub-chamber was added to the SEM. The top cover for the sub-chamber has a pinhole with a diameter of 1.5 mm through which the EB was irradiated on the samples. H_2 and CH_4 gases were supplied to the sub-chamber through a valve, which controls the flow rate. Reproduced from Kiyohara et al.[100] B) Schematic drawing of a 30 kV FEG-SEM equipped with dual-gas introduction system for fabrication of the nanorods by EBID with a mixture gas of iron carbonyl and ferrocene. Reproduced from Takeguchi et al.[127]

In contrast, laser-assisted patterning emerges as a powerful tool for microscale structuring, offering the advantages of high throughput and the possibility of in situ Raman spectroscopy, a capability particularly beneficial for real-time monitoring of structural and electronic changes in graphene during processing. Among these techniques, FEBID appears to hold the greatest promise in terms of direct-write capability, material selectivity, and threshold-based control over deposition processes. However, concerns persist about the quality of the graphene-like material deposited, particularly due to the incorporation of organic residues and low sp^2 content in the deposited films. Despite these limitations, FEBID remains a highly tunable and versatile approach, especially when coupled with post-deposition purification or graphitisation strategies.

5.1 Challenges to be addressed

One of the principal challenges in the domain of direct graphene writing lies in the ambiguity of what constitutes true "directness". Current approaches such as polymer-to-graphene conversion via electron or laser irradiation are only semidirect in nature, owing to their reliance on a prior deposition of a carbon-rich polymer precursor. Furthermore, these methodologies frequently require a post-irradiation thermal annealing step, often in inert or reducing environments, which further undermines the claim of directness. For a process to be genuinely direct, it would require the in situ graphitisation of ambient or gaseous carbonaceous species, such as atmospheric volatile organic compounds or through forming gas, without any precursor layer. Compounding this are issues of resolution: due to the optical transparency of monolayer and few-layer graphene, visualisation and pattern fidelity assessment remain non-trivial, demanding sophisticated techniques such as SEM, Raman mapping, or conductive AFM. Moreover, precise alignment of the written features, particularly in multilayer or device-integrated architectures, necessitates advanced stage control and fiducial referencing systems. Emerging techniques such as FEBID, FIBM (in particular HIBM), and laser-assisted direct writing present promising pathways, yet each carries limitations in terms of throughput, contamination, or control over crystallinity, thus warranting further investigation and refinement.

From a hardware perspective, the implementation of direct graphene writing within a scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with a thermionic electron gun, environmental chamber, gas injection system (GIS), a heating stage introduces and a picoamperometer a complex interplay of operational challenges and instrumental constraints. The thermionic gun, while robust and widely accessible, offers relatively lower brightness and spatial coherence compared to field emission sources, potentially limiting the achievable resolution in patterning and increasing interaction volumes, complicating control over lateral feature sizes

and edge sharpness. The environmental chamber, though indispensable for in situ gas-phase reactions or pressure-regulated processes, introduces complications in electron scattering and beam stability, thereby requiring precise regulation of chamber pressure and gas composition to mitigate image degradation and ensure beam fidelity.

The GIS, a critical enabler for introducing carbonaceous precursors or forming gas, can pose contamination risks if not finely calibrated, potentially leading to undesirable carbon deposition on non-targeted areas or even optical components such as electron lenses *etc.*. Additionally, the incorporation of a heating stage, essential for post-irradiation conversion or catalytic enhancement, demands thermal isolation and robust material compatibility to prevent off-gassing or structural warping under prolonged heating cycles.

Importantly, the BSD detector, often situated close to the sample chamber, is vulnerable to contamination from volatilised precursors or beam-induced sputtering in gas-rich environments. Prolonged exposure to reactive gases, especially under elevated temperatures and electron bombardment, can degrade detector sensitivity or induce fouling on sensitive components, including scintillators or photomultiplier tubes. Proper shielding, controlled gas flow paths, and regular maintenance schedules become imperative to protect detector integrity and overall instrument longevity. These multifaceted constraints underscore the necessity of carefully orchestrated hardware configurations and operational protocols to enable reliable, reproducible, and truly "direct" graphene writing in SEM platforms.

6 Future Work

Emerging directions in FEBID and LIG for graphene patterning reflect a confluence of technological innovation and sustainability considerations. Low-dose precursor-to-graphene strategies are being explored for patterning on flexible substrates, such as those used in paper-based electronics, enabling lightweight and disposable graphene-based devices. Hybrid workflows that integrate electron beam lithography with chemical vapour deposition (CVD) offer promising avenues for spatially selective doping, enhancing functionality at the nanoscale. The implementation of machine-learning algorithms to optimise beam patterning parameters is poised to significantly improve precision, throughput, and reproducibility simultaneously being able to avoid proximity effects, drifts *etc.* Concurrently, the development and deployment of environmentally benign precursors are gaining traction, driven by the imperative for sustainable and less hazardous e-beam processing protocols. Furthermore, the field is witnessing a growing interest in the identification and classification of graphitisable materials suitable for electron beam-induced deposition (EBID) of graphene. This necessitates a revised framework to guide the rational selection of precursors based on their structural evolution under electron irradiation.

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